

NIGERIA AND THE POLITICS OF GOD-FATHERISM: FROM MILITARY DICTATORSHIP TO CIVILIAN PLUTOCRACY

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Abstract

This study aims at examining Nigeria's political behaviour, which not only fails in its trial to shape the political spectrum and or polarity but also misconstrues the precise connotation of 'free choice and political freedom of the common people' as suggested by true liberal democracy. God-fatherism is being developed in a form of neo-dictatorial system of governance through the lens of free choice of the people by which dictatorial democracy – in a passive move of imposing oneself over others in various ways – proves its existence in today's Nigerian politics. This paper testifies that the Nigerian politicians and electorates misuse the unsurpassed provision of true liberal democracy, and thus turn the populace in a gravity of antagonism, fear, and prejudice. The study concludes that the multiparty system that aims at maximizing more political opening to cover wider opinions of the people so as to ensure general inclusiveness in political life constructs another side of intolerance and death-defying consequences against opposition groups. This continues to inculcate and or create a close affinity between democratically elected civilians and military dictators in the era of postcolonial Nigeria.

Keyword: *Military junta, plutocracy, Nigerian Politics, Democracy, Multiparty system*

Introduction: Nation at the Hands of Plutocrats

On the 08th of June, 1998, around 04 O'clock Nigerian time, radio stations played jingo, interrupting their scheduled routine programs to announce the death

of General Sani Abacha, the President and Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, at the State House, Aso Rock Villa, Abuja. Since Independence in the 1960, apart from nation building that tops (I suppose) any other probity,

regardless of any different facets, Nigeria has been facing a number of tough challenges including who should govern the affairs of the country, and how to govern those affairs for better Nigeria, and what should be the nature of this assiduous task (governing)? These, together with other inconsequential questions started to shape the future of Nigeria. Simultaneously, the multicultural nature that heavily concentrates on language, region and religion assimilates politics, economic and social consciousness of the people. The identities and not national objectives, determine the popularly great-three aspects (political system, economic policy, social development and conscience).

Over the course of so many decades, world states and nations have been under the leadership of various systems and regimes. Sometimes, by the evil despots. Perhaps, modernity and evolution brought about by different civilizations are responsible for these inevitable changes that shape today's human needs and behaviours. Tyranny, dictatorship, and absolutism of those maintaining their presence by means of subjugating and denying freedom of choice, were overwhelmingly overpowered by the forces of liberty and freedom.

Subsequently, in the 21st century, democracy appears to be a force and provenance of goliath derived out of selecting procedures for constituting government through a large body of representatives. From 1974 European

Portugal to 2010 North African Tunisia, the forces of freedom, equity and equality emerged in just three decades to conclude that the backbone of a regime not by forcing oneself, but by free choice of the populace, the majority of the citizens.

Political democracy cannot be extrapolated by a simple contestation or a voting behaviour. It depends on circumstantial series of procedural definitions of the system as adduced by Joseph Schumpeter, Samuel Huntington and Robert Dahl. Moreover, as per Huntington, systems often come through competitive selections, and yet less democratic. For example, the selection procedure that denied around 70 percent of the black South African people, or some 10 percent black Americans who were similarly banned to participate as part of society were some sort of dictatorial system of leadership, and undemocratic, however (Huntington, 1991).

In yet another unfortunate air in the balloon of democracy, an afterthought advocating slippery decline of democracy in Europe and Africa is proved to be firmly in place. The Economist Intelligence Unit suggests the following index to rank individual countries in terms of risen or fallen score of a nation:

The index, which comprises 60 indicators across five broad categories—electoral process and pluralism, functioning of

government, political participation, democratic political culture and civil liberties—concludes that less than 5% of the world’s population currently lives in a “full democracy”. Nearly a third live under authoritarian rule, with a large share of those in China. Overall, 89 of the 167 countries assessed in 2017 received lower scores than they had the year before (EIU, 2018).

This remains a palpable indication that democracy, perhaps, due to the poor performance in delivery, the quality of leaders in public offices is on recession, and thus declining in reverse. More than half of as much as 167 assessed nations scored lower than before. In Africa, hybrid regimes are rising to maintain powers by all the means including constitutional reforms.

Similarly, populism never champion Nigeria’s political democracy. The multicultural nature of the country plays a significant contribution, especially in the northern geo-political zone where people engage in politics to balance with the other parts of the country, rather than sincere commitment on what could bolster nation-building tools and strategies. This idea resorts to brinkmanship as it also furthers different experiences to the Nigeria’s peculiar transition to democracy, which is, according to Momoh (2003) being privatized depending on the personality in power, and thus not often based on the

provisions of the party system that ideally ought to get the fertile ground of its existence through general and common interest of the people.

More or so, the deviant nature of the Nigerian leaderships – both military regime and democratically elected civilians – contributes no progressive burgeon in terms of social well-being of the citizens, economic boosting or even the rampant corruption and other malpractices. Hence, there are no significant differences that have so far been recorded throughout Nigeria’s post-independence history. The country has therefore, never produced the leadership or system that was unanimously welcomed by the generic populace as there were also, no commitments by the few in power to ensure social welfare, security and equity between different social classes that the nation contains.

This might have always been the situation. According to Agbodike (2014), traditionally, tribal ethnicity and ego-centric weaknesses as well are put in place as prior agenda, and not national interests and Nigerian people. Perhaps, this peculiar attitude delays national development regardless of non-interrupted democracy of more than two decades in Nigeria. It is not the system of governments: civilian or military, but the leadership and particular behaviour of an individuals that are default on their portfolios.

Since embarking upon democracy in 1999, good governance and freedom of

choice are being replaced with power politics, due to a do-or-die brand of politics and God-fatherism. Nigeria, a sixty (60) years old nation – at the time of writing this paper - was also subject to military junta for more than three decades the country has never experienced a classless meritocracy where people climb to power based on their abilities, integrities and sincerities. However, despite regular elections and smooth transitions of power between different political groups, the system has not been able to put into an end to plutocracy in the system. Rather, the abysmal tradition of ‘who knows who’ not ‘what one does’ always prevails.

Methodology

Quantitative data analysis is applied to conduct this research. Books, journals and research reports compiled on plutocracy and bourgeoisies’ politics in Nigeria were consulted as sources of information. However, through observation, it is noticed that the politics of god-father overrides liberal politics where freedom for social development, cohesion and fairer sharing of power and wealth within a society is allowed. Of course, liberal democracy theory and fascism also guide this research to the conclusion, however.

Findings

On one hand, this study concludes that the fertile ground of the poor political institutions, and even corruption are the result of a bunch of amateurs saddled on

strategically important positions with less or no skills. Public office holders, simply because they are considered the boss remain in position to dictate over affairs of a particular political organization things can go awry with their personal lusts and nasty desires. This ensures disparity in the distribution of wealth, and a high rate of illiteracy. While in the other, it finalizes that the over-spending and embezzlement for the sake of winning majority has long term impact on the fates of millions of Nigerians. Nevertheless, it is argued that the cronyism nature of Nigeria’s officialdom turns large number of talented young people into a bunch of crooks. It also ensures that stalwart loyalists remain in serving the interests of godfathers rather than national objectives. This game is obviously dangerous, in fact, it implants and prolongs irregularities and dishonesty instead of patriotism.

Political Militarism

Political militarism is one of the main factors bridged the chasm between military regime and civilian leadership in Nigeria. Thus, the country yet fails to escape from the aberrant governing body. Upon the 1999 General Elections that brought former military Head of States, General Olusegun Obasanjo (rtd.) into power, Nigerians were optimistically hoping that the newly elected leaders under the headship of Obasanjo would discharge their duties by dismissing all types of bizarre cronyism and social injustice.

But it did not seem anything changed for opposing the policy of Nigerian ruling personalities could guarantee punishment against common man. Likewise, expressing one's mind especially that relates to politics may attract severe consequences. Political intolerance grows with time. Politicians as put by Agbodike (2014) sacrifice public safety for the interest of their political ambition as they appear to be so bigoted that they reject to accept any other political views than their own. Military, police and other security personnel are used to crack down and political opponents at all the times as soon they try to take a side other than that of the government. Several examples are cited that civil servants, especially at state level, were mistreated by thuggish-youths with shaven heads carrying cutlasses, axes, and clubs at various ministries and agencies threatening to hit the opponents from other political wings.

A membership to a non-ruling party is considered political crimes that are traditionally committed by the working class, often during the dawn of neo-plutocratic Nigeria. This tradition seems to nullify functional roles of multiparty system of political democratization, and thus engages in war with true liberal democracy and modernity.

In the history of the modern world; in fact, one of the ideas of democracy is that citizens have the right to freely decide their future by choosing leaders who can rescue the nation out of any potential danger. These rights in Nigeria

seem to be limited to only those in the ruling party, for example, the Army, police and other paramilitary officers at the services of those in power, and not general populace. The elected civilians who ought to govern affairs of the country for economic and social developments are seizing the chance to run what appears to be a quasi-fascist government. Rule of law is being subverted by brutal sentimentalism of an oligarchy that personalize and confiscate what belong to everybody.

The Politics of Cabalism and the Hopes of Sanguine Nigerians

Scholars are on the endless debates to what a precise definition of democracy is. But they unanimously agree that if the system is to prevail, it should be guided by free, fair and periodic elections through a mode of competitive selection based on equality between the electorates and contestants. However, instead of equal participation in decision making processes, the constellation of cabals – with no civil service or political portfolios – invade the affairs of the government from behind the scene. For example, during the post-2015 presidential election that brought Muhammadu Buhari, from All Progressives Congress (APC) political platform into power by winning the majority votes; it was allegedly believed that the government activities were so much influenced by a clique of obscure bee at a time when the country was sinking into an abyss of lawlessness, nepotism corruption and violence.

Aisha Buhari, the spouse of Nigeria's President, Muhammadu Buhari, in an interview with British Broadcasting Cooperation (BBC) Hausa, in October, 2016 declared that:

“The President does not know forty five (45) out of fifty (50) of the people he appointed (ministers, directors, chairmen of ministries, agencies and parastatals) and I don't know them either, despite being his wife for twenty seven (27) years... some people are sitting down in their homes folding their arms only for them to be called to come and head an agency or a ministerial position...” (BBC, 2016)

Since then onward, speculations were rife as to the lack of mutual consciousness between President Muhammadu Buhari's family and that of Mamman Daura. Mamman Daura, a nephew to President Buhari, was allegedly charged by Mrs. Buhari with misusing orders and directives on behalf, and in the absence of the President, even without his consent. Mamman Daura, through the presidential spokesperson, Garba Shehu gave some executive commands including scrapping the First Lady's office. Aisha Buhari however, denounced some officials and charged them with deploying their responsibilities to other channel rather than their main duty stations. Her accusation statement reads:

“Nigeria's development is hinged on the ability of public officials to execute their mandates professionally and to be shining examples in their various areas of endeavour. It is not good sign when officials abandoned their responsibility and start clutching at straw...the spokesperson of the President has the onerous responsibility of managing the image of the President and all good works that he is executing in the country. Rather than face his responsibility squarely, he has shifted his loyalty from the President to others who have no stake in the compact that the President signed with Nigerians on May 02, 2015 and 2019” (Premium times, 2019)

On Mamman Daura, who many Nigerians believe to be one of the strongest men within the circle of cabalists of aides, Aisha tongued out as she is quoted saying:

“We all remember that the chief proponent appropriated to himself and his family a part of the Presidential Villa, where he stayed for almost four (4) years and the time came for him to leave, he orchestrated and invaded my family's privacy through a video circulated by Mamman's daughter, Fatima, the public was given the impression that on arrival into the country I was locked out of the Villa by

Mr. President” (Premium times, 2019).

These incidents have an automatic, in a way or the other, contradiction with the popular saying of Muhammad Buhari in his first address to the nation soon after taking the oath of office: “I belong to everybody, and I belong to nobody” (Muhammadu Buhari, 2015) as the ‘*Cabalism Politik*’ seems to be thriving within the State House vacuum, thereby reshaping a new version of intra-family politics immediately after the incumbent President assumed duty. The presidency on December 23, 2019, asserted that having cabals is not a censurable thing at all. The Punch daily newspaper published on its page that “the Presidency has announced that there is nothing wrong in having cabals around the President, Muhammadu Buhari, to help him run the government” (Punch, 23 December, 2019), but the word ‘cabal’, which connotes informal intermingling interference in the government affairs, seems to be missing in the Nigeria’s constitution. Perhaps, that is what Mrs. Buhari was trying to prove in her early warnings and calls for attention.

God-Fatherism: The Sign of Incipient Plutocracy and Corruption

“Man is born free, but everywhere he is in chains” (Rousseau: 1712-1778), “Nature placed mankind under the governance of two sovereign masters: pain and pleasure...” (Jeremy Bentham: 1748-1832). The contents and contextual meanings of these and other similar

intellectual afterthoughts equip democracy to emerge as the best system to govern the global societies, seemingly. Welfarism, maximizing happiness for the greatest number of people, bolster the waves of democracy to success. Until today, very small amount of freedom, fairness in the elections or even on who to contest are so far being distilled into the process if one is to examine as many nations as possible, especially in the third world including in Nigeria.

Humankind loves freedom, naturally. Freedom that enshrines free expression, articulation, and movement. Ipso facto, democracy, up to this time, is favoured over other types of leadership because of its campaign towards liberty and equal participation in decision making and forming the government of common interests.

On the other hand, just as he loves freedom, man or human desires to occupy, control and oversee the affairs of other fellow human. This contradictory nature of individuals puts global politics at danger where wickedness, selfishness and brutality govern the world affairs.

Likewise, this very wickedness and egocentric means of personal interest drags Nigeria’s domestic political circumstances to the state of plutocracy instead of compassionate sincerity, equal participation in political life between decision-making minority and the populous citizenry. Meanwhile, this, as a factor, brings about a perplexing continuation of God-fatherism in modern

Nigerian politics. Participating and or contesting for the election merely by membership of a political group, dispassionately neutral without the support of any God-father is far becoming a near impossibility in Nigerian politics.

Democracy more than any other system of governance is a set of apparatus that tries to imply respect for the rule of law and justice. This considerable paramount part of democracy is proved absent in contemporary Nigerian political democratization, and in exchange, corruption takes over. Corruption has negative implication on democracy and causes sluggish progress in terms of conducting free and fair election. This is why free-floating elections seem seldom in Nigeria. Hence, rigging becomes the tradition among political parties, collation officers and other stakeholders, with the result that malfeasance leads to bad governance and failure in leadership.

To contest for the election as far as the Nigeria's Electoral Act (2010) is concerned one needs to be a full registered member of one of the registered political groups. The section 87 (1), (2), and (3) of the Act, provides that nominating a candidate by a political group should be based on primary; directly or indirectly, should the party has more than aspirants. And thus, a candidate cannot nominate him/herself against any elective position across levels.

Consequently, contestant should, conditionally, be nominated by the party. Apropos what is provided in the electoral act (2010), lobbying hard in persuading politician and functionary so they can pave the way for you in order for your talent and capacity get publicised is rather de trop.

In modern day Nigeria, politics that leads to forming government through competitive elections by a freely choice of the masses becomes stuffs of bourgeoisies. A clique of few affluent creditworthiness possess the political ascendancy, and thus, control decision-making even when they seem out of the circle. To climb into political position, one must win legalization that recognises their legitimacy. In other words, political organizations are sponsored by those wealthiest individuals, and party's interests always are built in coalescing with the real objectives of the same wealthiest or god-fathers. Regrettably, this tragedy opened up Pandora's Box of domestic political instability including insurgency, kidnapping and banditry that consume lives of thousands of people, combine.

Shehu (2015) hypothesizes that meaningful development is always hampered by political corruption on the account that the bribes are taken by the top ranking officials in government (Shehu, 2015). This justifies multiple facets to the current perilous state of the country. Frankly, since Independence, Nigerian politics is being seen as a type of modern capital investment where

rights of the people, welfare and infrastructures are snatched by the politicians. Quest for bread of the day makes it easy for them to divide and rule in a form of subjugating attitude over the people that they as far as theological teaching and democratic value are concerned are supposed to be taking care of.

Conclusion

Nigeria as a nation can be identified as a country with freakish nature, simply because in terms of what one sees, a basic necessity in good governance, patriotism, social and economic developments; are lacking. There is seldom any significant differences between military junta and civilian administration. Those who vocalize the absolute ends merely maximize happiness at the expense of the large number of weaker class of the society. Both military dictators that imposed themselves forcefully and democratically elected civilians seize the chance to galvanize massive casualties, create imbalance and starvation countrywide. In both of the systems, the nature of intolerance and crackdown were up against any pressure group.

Regrettably, regardless of the type of leadership in the place, family background, lineage and other type of social classes and priorities determine fate of Nigerians when it comes to the issue of civil services, appointments, transfers and administrations, and not merit, competency, integrity and

intellectual matching that fits available post to be filled. This type of plague is not limited to the civil services, but is found across the units of the nation from top to bottom; federal, states and local authorities. Thus, it is not skills that guide one's successful story in government, but family, tribe or region. This unfortunately unjustifiable tradition brings about disability to equalize between the citizens. Injustice and brutal selfishness are becoming major threats always trying to handover Nigeria to insurgent groups, bankruptcy, and underdevelopment, permanently.

Recommendations

- Nigeria is a country blessed with both human and natural resources, to utilize these blissful natures, justice and equity should be reliable apparatus applied in government-people relations.
- Rule of law should guide activities of Nigerians in common, regardless of the class one belongs to
- Freedom and the respect of human rights should not be lines on the papers, but be recognized by day-to-day interactions of the people individually and collectively, formally and informally.
- National interests should be foremost than any other personal interests of whoever personality that answers the name 'Nigerian'

- Priority should be given to skills, talent, intelligence and experience rather than family, background, lineage and region or tribe.
- Equal opportunity, and chance should be assured to every citizen as provided by the national legal documents. This will assure integrity, patriotism, sincerity and hardwork. Nevertheless, the long-lasting peaceful Nigeria with swift progressive development across spheres of life would become a thing
- of reality rather than a dream or imaginary mirage.
- A clarion call for the leaders, serve your people far better than your services to your immediate family, spouse, child or nephew. It would turn back to you with peace of mind, love, proud and joy. As thanks giving, you would be adored not just by your family, but also by millions of people that you served including your friends and relatives.
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